

Estimating Disposal Canister Numbers for Spent Nuclear Fuel: Insights from the Swiss Cost Study 2026

Solans V^{1,*}, Pudollek S¹, Shama A¹, Vlassopoulos E¹

¹Nagra, Hardstrasse 73, Wettingen, Switzerland;

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ABSTRACT

Every five years, Nagra, the Swiss nuclear waste management organisation, must perform a cost study for the final disposal of Swiss radioactive waste to ensure that the waste owners can cover future costs related to decommissioning and waste disposal. The next cost study is to be published in 2026. One of the required tasks for the cost study is the estimation of the number of disposal canisters for spent nuclear fuel (SNF). The number of canisters is one of the leading factors of costs, as it determines the size of the geological repository, the amount of rock to be excavated, the operational timeline of the different facilities (both at the surface and underground), etc. This paper presents the methodology for inferring the number of disposal canisters, along with all the steps involved. Therefore, this paper presents the construction of an SNF database for this cost study, based on the different scenarios, whose boundary conditions cover different operational times forecast for Swiss nuclear power plants. Then, the estimation of decay heat evolution up to 1 million years for each spent nuclear fuel assembly is presented. Finally, the methodology for canister loading optimisation using the spent nuclear fuel assemblies characteristics, including decay heat and transport casks loadings, for this cost study is shown.

Keywords: SNFs, decay heat, canisters, cost study

1. INTRODUCTION

In Switzerland, the cost of decommissioning nuclear facilities and disposing of nuclear waste must be paid by the waste producers, which is based on the “polluter pays” principle. To ensure sufficient financial resources are available at the time of decommissioning and disposal, two funds have been established: the “Decommissioning Fund” and the “Waste Disposal Fund”. These funds are state-controlled and are regulated by Swiss laws. Both funds have been operating under the name Stenfo, which acts with autonomy and is affiliated with the Federal Department of Environment, Transport, Energy and Communication. Nuclear waste producers are obligated to contribute to these funds and remain legally responsible for the decommissioning and disposal of the waste they produce.

To evaluate whether the funds are sufficient to cover all future costs, a cost study is conducted every five years. Swissnuclear, the association of all Swiss nuclear power operators, coordinates these cost studies. The next cost study will be publicly available via Swissnuclear at the end of 2026.

Even though the results of the cost study 2026 are only published at the end of the year, cost calculations have been started months prior on a well-established methodology [1]. Nagra, the waste management organisation of Switzerland, is responsible for assessing the cost for different scenarios. Cost distribution between the waste producers is regulated by cost keys, though waste amount estimates are attributed directly to the respective waste producers. This is also true for assigning disposal canister numbers to respective spent nuclear fuel owners.

*Email address: Virginie.solans@nagra.ch

In this paper, only the aspects related to the disposal of spent nuclear fuel assemblies (SNFs) will be presented. The cost of SNFs disposal is strongly linked to the number of disposal canisters required. The cost impact is not only linked to the price of the canister itself, but also to its consequences, such as the amount of space needed to be excavated underground, operational time required from the surface and underground facilities, etc.

This paper details, in general terms, the steps required to obtain the number of canisters for cost study 2026. First, the establishment of the different scenarios taken into account for the cost study is explained in Section 2. Section 3 presents the creation of an SNF database. Section 4 details the depletion calculations using the SNF database previously established, leading to decay heat evolution of individual SNFs. The number of canisters is then derived for each nuclear power plant (NPP). This methodology is explained in Section 5. Implications of these calculations for cost study 2026 are explained in Section 6.

2. SCENARIOS

In Switzerland, three commercial NPPs are currently in operation, with four reactor cores (Leibstadt, Gösgen and Beznau NPPs). One NPP has already shut down (Mühleberg NPP). Mühleberg NPP started decommissioning in December 2019. The shutdown of the reactor cores of Beznau NPP was announced for 2032 for Unit 2 and 2033 for Unit 1. For the two other NPPs, Leibstadt and Gösgen, their decommissioning date is unknown, but not foreseen to be in the near future.

In order to reflect the impact of operational times of the NPPs on cost estimations, different scenarios have been defined by Stenfo. Operational times of 50 and 60 years of the NPPs Leibstadt and Gösgen are to be considered. For the Beznau NPPs 60 years (as 50 operational years are already passed) and 63 years (taking into account the announced shutdown dates) are to be considered. A scenario with 70 years operational time is to be assessed in a qualitative manner in the upcoming cost study for the first time.

The different scenarios considered for the cost study not only define different operational times for the NPPs but also include boundary conditions on the operation of the deep geological repository (DGR). Operation of the Swiss DGR is not foreseen for several decades; therefore, no design of the DGR has been fixed yet. Only the location of the DGR has been proposed by Nagra with the general license application (RBG) that was submitted in November 2024, and the chosen location in the Nördlich Lägern region has been taken up by Stenfo in the scenario boundary conditions. The review of the general license application fixing the site of the DGR is, at the time of writing, under review by the Swiss authorities (ENSI). The design of the DGR for the base scenario of cost study 26 is based on the RBG, which was made publicly available in 2025.

3. SNF DATABASE

The information regarding past, current and future SNFs has been communicated by the NPPs directly to Nagra. This aims to have a realistic description of the inventory for each of the defined scenarios. The information communicated includes a list of SNFs already discharged, the current SNFs in operation, and their plan for future operations. This also includes their strategy for their last core operations, and different lists of future SNFs depending on the different scenarios for the operational time of each NPP. The type of information provided includes (non-exhaustive list) the name of the SNF (if available), design of the SNF, initial enrichment, initial mass, burnup, discharge date, and cycle information. An example of the evolution of the SNFs' burnup depending on the discharge date for a Swiss nuclear power plant is presented in Figure 1. The last core strategy is clearly visible in Figure 1. Around 12'000 SNFs are planned to be disposed of in Switzerland.

Figure 1 Burnup evolution depending on the discharge date for a Swiss NPP.

On top of the information required for the depletion calculations, it is necessary to know in which transport casks the SNF is (or will be) placed into. Indeed, in Switzerland, transport and storage casks are used for the interim storage of SNFs, once they are discharged from the storage pool at the NPPs. These casks, once they leave the site of the NPP, are located mainly at ZWILAG, the centralised interim storage facility or at ZWIBEZ, the interim storage facility at Beznau NPP.

4. DEPLETION CALCULATIONS

Using the SNF database described in the last section, depletion calculations are performed to infer quantities of interest, especially decay heat. The depletion calculations are done using SCALE [2]. SCALE is a code suite developed by Oak Ridge National Laboratory in the US. SCALE 6.3.1 using the ORIGEN-ARP modules and ENDF/B VII.1 was used for depletion calculations. One of the challenges of this work is the number of calculations required, which necessitates software capable of performing depletion calculations efficiently, especially regarding the number of scenarios with the different operational times of the NPPs.

One of the outputs of the depletion calculations is a decay heat matrix for each of the scenarios. For each of the SNFs, the decay heat is calculated from their discharge date up to 1 million years.

This time evolution is important for the performance and safety assessment of the geological repository on a large time scale. However, it is also important to know the time evolution at a lower time scale. For instance, as the encapsulation facility will be running for several years, it is important to know the decay heat evolution to better optimise the canister loading.

Indeed, two SNFs can have the same decay heat at one point in time but for different reasons. For instance, it could be an MOX SNF, where its decay heat is evolving relatively slowly due to its fuel

composition and long cooling time. Or it could be a UO₂ SNF that was discharged from the reactor core recently. In that case, the decay heat might be the same one day, but their decay heat evolution is very different. A UO₂ SNF at short cooling time will decay much faster than a MOX SNF with a long time. Therefore, after several years, these two SNFs will have significantly different decay heat values. On the optimisation side, it is usually more optimal to encapsulate an SNF with a short cooling time toward the end of the encapsulation facility's operation rather than at the beginning. For the MOX SNF, this distinction is less important.

Figure 2 Histogram of the decay heat from all Swiss SNFs in 2026.

Figure 2 shows the decay heat of the Swiss SNFs in 2026. It is clear that the BWR SNFs have smaller decay heat values, but this is due to their SNFs having lower initial fissile mass. This is why, in the canister design developed for RBG (and used in cost study 2026), one can place up to 12 BWR SNFs per canister or 4 PWR SNFs. The PWR SNFs in figure 2 with very high decay heat are MOX SNFs.

For the RBG safety case a decay heat limit of 1500W was considered for the derivation of the number of final disposal canisters and their representative inventory and properties (especially decay heat). For the cost study 2026, due to further developments and refinements of the project the limit of 1500W was studied, as well as higher decay heat limits per canister.

5. CANISTER LOADINGS

Once the decay heat evolution of the SNFs has been calculated, the canister loading can be computed. A realistic canister loading includes several constraints that must be fulfilled. First, the transport and interim storage casks need to be considered. The number of docking stations considered to be available in the hot cell of the encapsulation facility, where the SNFs will be repackaged from their transport casks and placed in their disposal canister, is a relevant parameter. The optimisation algorithm that determines the order in which to empty the transport casks and then determines the combination of the SNFs to dispose of, is called SIMAN-3.

SIMAN-3 is an in-house tool designed for the canister loading optimization (an older version has been described in [3]). It is based on the Branch-and-Bound algorithm. The results of the canister loading optimisation tool depend mostly on the boundary conditions of the scenario but also on the parameters of the algorithm. The parameters of the algorithm (such as maximum optimisation time allowed at each optimisation step) have been fixed for all calculations related to the cost study.

The main boundary conditions for the canister loading are as follows. For all of them it is worthwhile to bear in mind that these boundary conditions will evolve in the future based on the continued development of the repository concept and design as well as the underlying safety case and performance assessment considerations:

- Canister design. The canister design defines the number of BWR or PWR SNFs that can be placed in each canister, as well as the decay heat limit per canister. The decay heat of each canister is calculated by summing the decay heat from the SNFs placed inside. The canister design considered for RBG as well as the base scenarios for cost study 2026 has 12 BWR SNFs or 4 PWR SNFs. One decay heat limit considered in both RBG and cost study is set to 1500W.
- Starting date of the encapsulation facility. A later starting date implies a lower decay heat of the SNFs to be encapsulated; therefore, it usually means a lower number of canisters. Currently, this parameter is set to 2062 in all scenarios for cost study 2026.
- Number of canisters that can be encapsulated each year at the facility. This value is currently set to 200 canisters per year. This is directly impacting the number of years of operation of the encapsulation facility. Long operational time means higher maintenance and operational costs for the facility; however, it also leads to lower decay heat averages as the additional time allows for some decay.
- The NPP operational time. If the nuclear power plants operate for longer time frames, a higher number of SNFs is produced, leading to a higher number of canisters, but also, given a set starting date for encapsulation operation, the time between discharge date and start of encapsulation is reduced, which leads to SNFs with higher decay heat. Within the work for cost study 2026 the scenarios defined by Stenfo are taken into account (see Section 2).
- Number of docking stations for the transport and interim storage casks. As the repackaging takes place in a hot-cell, the transport casks need to be moved from their interim storage to this hot-cell in the encapsulation facility. The SNFs that are then placed in the disposal canisters are chosen among the transport casks docked at the encapsulation facility. Therefore, a higher number of docking stations allows for better mixing between different casks and consequently for a better optimisation of the canister loading, thus reducing the overall number of canisters. However, it comes at a price of the size of the encapsulation plant. This size will be set based on the general license application, which considers three docking stations.

It is important to notice that in general, i.e. outside the variants of cost study, these boundary conditions are not independent of each other, which is why a holistic optimisation tool is required for defining optimal boundary conditions with respect to an efficient final disposal and waste management programme. Nagra has been developing a tool for the exploration of the effects of different combinations of parameters of the DGR, as it is crucial to understand how each boundary condition interacts with each other. This in-house tool is called ROWO [4].

For instance, in the case of canister loading, increasing the decay heat limit is not always beneficial. Indeed, a canister loading is constrained by the number of SNFs it can hold, but also by its decay heat limit. So, a canister can be “full” if all its positions are filled or if the decay heat limit is reached. The limiting factor depends on the scenario; in the case of short operation times of all Swiss nuclear power plants, the decay heat of all SNFs tends to be small because the time between discharge and encapsulation is high. In opposition, long operation times lead to high decay heat and usually higher burnup, too, resulting in a limitation on decay heat rather than spacing with the same canister design and encapsulation facility start. Increasing the decay heat limit will increase the ratio of canisters filled by spacing rather than decay heat, up to the point where all canisters are completely filled (without

empty positions). In that case, increasing the decay heat indefinitely no longer contributes to reduced numbers of canisters. However, decay heat limits are dependent on the multi-barrier system and canister design choices, such as its size and are governed mainly by the near-field properties.

6. IMPLICATIONS TO THE COST STUDY

For the cost study, the objective is not only to reach the minimum number of canisters for each scenario but also to assign the appropriate number of canisters to each NPP. This assignment is impacted by the number of SNFs produced by each NPP, but also the decay heat of their SNFs.

In order to create this fair share distribution, a methodology based on the fair share utilisation of the encapsulation has been developed. This methodology has already been used in previous cost studies. The definition of fair share utilisation in this methodology is based on the assumption of a continuous fair share encapsulation over time, excluding NPP-selective later or earlier encapsulation. Therefore, the number of canisters encapsulated each year is divided between the nuclear power plants based on the number of SNFs, the type of SNFs (BWR or PWR), and the average SNF decay heat at the time of encapsulation.

One other output from the canister loading algorithm is the decay heat evolution of the canisters. The decay heat of a canister is the sum of the decay heat of the SNFs placed inside. This decay heat evolution is calculated up to 1 million years. For each scenario, a representative canister for each type (BWR, UO₂ PWR and MOX PWR), created from all the computed canisters, is inferred. This decay heat evolution is an important input for the safety and performance assessment of the DGR.

Figure 3 shows the decay heat evolution for the UO₂ PWR canisters, up to 1 million years. In light grey are the individual canisters, and in black, the representative canister is shown. The decay heat evolution depends on the fuel composition, which is tightly linked to the operating conditions of each reactor.

Figure 3 Decay heat evolution of UO₂ PWR canisters up to 1 million years with their representative canister.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper presented the methodology to obtain the number of canisters necessary for Nagra's 2026 cost study. The first step was to define the relevant parameters and boundary conditions based on the scenarios to be studied in this cost study, the DGR cost-study project realization and the operational time of the different NPPs. Based on the cost-study scenarios the NPPs communicated details about the SNFs corresponding to each scenario, including SNFs not yet utilised. From the established database, depletion calculations using SCALE were performed to determine the decay heat evolution of individual SNFs. The canister loading, thus also the total number of canisters, can be computed knowing the SNFs' decay heat evolution and design parameters of the encapsulation facility. On top of the total number of canisters, the number of canisters for the different NPPs, depending on their SNFs' characteristics, could be attributed.

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